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RESEARCH OF HISTORICAL CITY CENTERS I

Jurayeva Elvira Elmuradovna is a senior teacher

Ma'murjonov Shukrullo Umidjon is a student

Samarkand State University of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Uzbekistan . Email address:
elvira8790@mail.ru

Abstract. Historical city and in general historical population places centers location geometric and a functional point of view from the point of view analysis done . Usually , cities or another population of places general (general city or common village) community center his geometric center in place that they are located study Big population in places common from the center except of the city to the parts belongs to special centers too is available will be. City centers common and special functionality point of view in terms of trade , ideological , pilgrimage , enlightenment and different types separated . Centers level to the whole city relatively when received sometimes big the area occupies For example , in Khiva's Ichan fortress center (residence from houses piece area) quite place occupation reached. Historical of cities in the composition position (hierarchy) in terms of different to the degree have has been centers there is Functionality according to the whole city center , dacha centers and neighborhood centers separate appropriate will be Architectural and artistic in terms of centers different , large - small complexes in the form of to be the possibility was considered .

Key words : square , castle, forum, city, town hall, agora,

Introduction Citywide center most of the city between , geometric in the center will be located . Functionally , it is wide comprehensive will be In itself social , trade and ideological-ideological processes incarnate is enough. Historical centers in line separately seats of the city administrative defense structures and socio-political fields occupies Administrative - defense structures Medium East in countries diz , castle , arch , horde like names with , castle, citadel , detinets, chrome, kremlin in European countries like names with called bride Socio-political fields more suitable town hall, krasnaya ploshchad , agora, forum, registon names with called Citywide in the center trading environment - the market priority place occupied _ Main market usually Chorsu name with called his appearance not only trade , but also handicrafts release devices also set . From the main market except for them in the corner special goods with trade specialized to be done there were markets . For example , in Tashkent Samarkand gate in front of Melon market , Orda nearby Cream market fao liyat showed was

Historical the whole city center complexes and facilities sometimes of cities big part take over came Center developed historical cities in line Opposite center separate stands [Nasriddinov Q. ...; Pulatov H., Shukurov A. ...; Nishanov M. ...].

Opposite shahristoni - his castle appearance basically of the city central in the part Registan area (" Area surh "), southern in the part Horde complexes and them connected Bridlehouse area with defined . Registan - of the city between the 14th and 16th centuries formed . Registan to the shape of the city gates and Horde (some researchers to the assumptions according to Quebec Khan palace) locations effect showed . Registan of the area stage basically two building : Odina building and his opposite Abdullah Khan Madrasa from volumes organize found was Square apparently Chorsu building , cistern and bathroom too important effect showed . Later XVIII-XX centuries in their heads this in the place , that is, Odina's home and Abdullah Khan Madrasa around them one how much smaller in volumes another madrasahs that's it it was said that they are also XIX-XX centuries in their heads field to art weighty contributions added To the square take going road on the edge small volume forms - stores to the complex completeness give reached was

Opposite city Registan another in cities such from complexes different to himself special aspect , his Medium in Asia an important caravan route with directly is dependent . Trade in Registan importance size Chorsu , cistern , bathroom proof Registon of the area volume-spatial in the composition

majestic of buildings from the surroundings place received more wonderful madrasa and mosques participation reached such as Abdullah Khan of madrasa on the sides Chariboy and Sayid Qulboy madrassas set up has been was

Archaeological findings Opposite one of the 1st half of the 14th century how much tiler buildings is available from being proof gives The city in the second half of the XIV century fortress the wall with wrapped , Odina mosque was built . The wall around 2.5-3 m deep ditch was dug up . Trench 4 above do not raise bridge was _ Shahrstan area a total of 40 hectares organize reached was XVI in the century city nearby big Prayer room mosque , bathroom height raised . Hungarian scientist Herman Vambery in 1863 Opposite there are 10 caravanserais in the city and big market that it was writes _

Registan in the complex come out priority importance architectural and artistic tools through too expression done was _ Jome level field from the level seven to the stairs higher up has been and " Kovush " in front of it pattob " (prayer their songs to be omitted) input place organized was. This place porch as done being , columns core carving with decorated and chair from marble processed was _ Ivan Amir During the time of Olim Khan (1910-1920). repaired known [Nasriddinov ..., p. 79].

Opposite , most of them are in the Emirate of Bukhara the throne successors residence they did This case Horde (" Ark " , "Inner fortress " as well). said) in his honor too reflection reached was _ His The shape is trapezoidal 2.2 ha area occupied _ Get up Storage gate of the city main Handle gate like ripe of brick , two side bouquet , vinegar decorative , top brown was _ Oral to information according to the roof on top of the emirate power target - with whip _ _ _ set placed was _ City mirshabs chief room this is also Sakhlov gate next to was _ Gate in the hallway solemn in days Opposite like relatives , officials row pulling standing for used . Against of the emir himself came at times it is Storage gate roof under sitting down crime level looking execution of sentences (amnesty , fine, flogging , execution) . observed [Nasriddinov ..., pages 101-102].

Horde one how many from the yard consists of was _ In the first domed mosque , divan, treasury rooms , tabla (saiskhana) , pigeon house was _ Second in the yard Get up main official the building was Arzkhona (reception) . was _ of the reception in front of preshayvan his own ornaments with separately separate standing Get up in the south garden is available

was Q. Nasriddinov in detail according to the " watershed " principles based on made up ekan : in the middle - marble pool , to him four by take went avenues between there were four " chamans " .

Get up southern in the part the ball arrows , arrow medicine (gunpowder) and another that's it similar rooms (arsenal) and one of Mongolian (Kebek Khan). grave was This grave named " Karshi " . According to Babur Mirza, it means " cave " . hint to be can The word " against " means " palace " . means said guess too there is Bridlehouse of the area southwest on the side Horde , northeast on the side Treasury is located was of the field north- west by to Registon south - east by Waterfall to the gate passed . Bridlehouse in the field usually for 7 days people numbers being standing , different performances organized , emir , bek decrees announcement done , execution done Dungeon too To the bridle near in the place from Registon of the city in the southeast Waterfall to the gate keep going of the road two on the side Oliy , Nur , Shermuhammad madrassas amir Haidar during built and later their around them shops row to the body came was The bridle room To the middle opposite on the side another administrative complex - Kazikhana name with called facility built Facility gatehouse and his in the yard two building : directly Treasury and Embassy from the buildings consists of was Treasury gate Storage from the gate different like sorry has been was Gatehouse the roof under on the porch three big drum standing From the porch city important at events trumpet players , trumpet players , circle players too used Treasury yard too marble with a pool garden , flower garden as that's it done was of the yard one on the side Treasury (judge office) , opposite Embassy built was Both building too one how

much from the rooms consists of in front of carving and painting with decorated porch is available was Treasury to the composition reception , Embassy to the composition a miracle bathroom entered Against of the emirate important military-strategic majbu - of the riyat loaded city and in rabad defense of constructions in architecture too own on the contrary found There too one how many from the buildings bullet drug , ball storage for used about above said was Ethnographic to information according to in the city total large (7 tires) and The number of small (5- seater) soldier 's rooms was 70 : 20 of them 50 in the city in rabad was _ Registon four side too barracks surrounded standing this of the field separately from being protected a tree gives [Nasriddinov ..., p. 109].

City area before the 1st M son period
2-The territory of the city from the Mongol period

Shahristan fortress of the wall in the corners in the constellations one each , gates 2-3 on top balls installed was Main Handle

gate on top and always 3 balls standing Shahristan outside special built big and small ballrooms too is available was City in his life international and local tradesman played a big role . During the period of Amir Olim Khan (1910-1920 years). Waterfall gate construction relationship with , to him near in the area from afar , that is from abroad coming merchants for Haftanob (name seven tanob land that he occupied hint) caravanserai built _ Weekly to the composition gatehouse , " Suvloq ", " Bedakhana ", " Stokhona ", " Philkhana " (in elephants too they came together), " Suvloq " (pool), " Tuyakamaq " . names with called building , structure and open environments (areas) entered was _

Closer up coming merchants and to the guests Rabotak guzari in the west bigger and Master Bright cemetery nearby smaller caravanserais service did

Opposite from the inner market of the city except again two Upper (large , east on the side) and Lower (smaller , west on the) markets activity showed . Of the two too in the composition almshouses was Big and small markets many shops and open field (specialized small market) . consists of was

Medium Asia , including of Uzbekistan historical in cities more centers most big architectural complex as formed . They are ideological - ideological to the function have was in Tashkent Chorsu architectural complex the whole city ideological-ideological function did it If so , His Holiness Imam , Sheikh Hovandi Tahir , Zangi Father , Zainuddin grandmother complexes suitable respectively Sebzor , Shayhontahir , Beshyogoch , Kokcha of the ideological - ideological functions done increased These are inside Shaikhontahir center separately place occupied This center common attention in terms of in Tashkent From Chorsu the next is the second center was Neighborhood centers " guzar " name in architecture with fire to the goal is appropriate . The word " guzar ". dictionary in terms of " transition the meaning of "place " . means Some the word " guzar " in books spatial in terms of continuously has been one how many of the neighborhood center in the sense of given Neighborhood centers - most of them

consisted of structures such as a neighborhood mosque, a pool, a teahouse, and several shops. Next period in his studies neighborhood mosque in the composition too shop like devices to be possible shown (Note 8). Some neighborhoods in the center a miracle madrasa , mausoleum , social service show like buildings too was

Figure 2. Reconstruction of the historical center of Samarkand city

Buildings in the neighborhood centers are interconnected in various combinations, creating unique spatial and spatial complexes.

Conclusion One of the characteristics of the Central Asian reconstruction is that it is not a functional, but an ideological-ideological factor. It is no coincidence that at the beginning of the 18th century, Shahmuradbi started the reconstruction works in Samarkand by restoring the shrines that have been venerated there since ancient times.

All, including non-monumental buildings and structures built in the recent past, are affected by the reconstruction process. Most of them are modernized. In Uzbekistan - in Tashkent, Samarkand, Andijan, Karshi and many other historical cities have considerable experience in reconstruction. To show them clearly is one of the educational tasks. Today, there is a need to discover all aspects of architectural and urban planning heritage that have not yet been fully revealed and to develop scientific and methodological measures and recommendations that should be applied to them. Among the urgent tasks in the field of architectural education are the tasks of

creating truly modern, full-fledged educational complexes and testing them, taking into account the achievements of world science.

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MUNDARIJA

	1– SHO‘BA. "SHAHAR HUDUDLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ARXITEKTURA VA SHAHAR MUHITINING SHAKLLANISHI VA KOMPLEKS RIVOJLANISHI"	
1.	Садиков Нематджон Исмаилович, Садикова Ситора-бону Нематджоновна КРИТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ КОНКУРСНЫХ ПРОЕКТОВ «ЦЕНТРА ТЮРКСКОГО МИРА В ГОРОДЕ ТУРКЕСТАН»	4-9
2.	Али Марва Мохамед Ханафи , Шукуров И.С, ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ГЕОРАДАРА «ЛЮЗА» В ГРАДОСТРОИТЕЛЬСТВЕ И РЕКОНСТРУКЦИИ ИСТОРИЧЕСКИХ ГОРОДОВ	10-15
3.	U.R.Oktyabirov, WORLD EXPERIENCE ON URBAN PLANNING SPHERE	16-20
4.	Шукуров И.С., Маракулина С.П, ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ТИПА ЖИЛОЙ ЗАСТРОЙКИ ДЛЯ ТЕРРИТОРИЙ СО СЛОЖНЫМ РЕЛЬЕФОМ. ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ	21-23
5.	Оленьков Валентин Данилович, Ятимов Илхом Абдурозикович, Колмогорова Алена Олеговна, ЛАНДШАФТНО-КЛИМАТИЧЕСКИЕ УСЛОВИЯ ТЕРРИТОРИИ РЕСПУБЛИКИ ТАДЖИКИСТАНА С ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕМ ГОРОДОВ С ЖАРКИМ ВЕТРОВЫМ И ЖАРКИМ ШТИЛЕВЫМ КЛИМАТОМ	24-27
6.	Камалова Дильноза Зайнидиновна ¹ , Файзуллаева Нодира Найимовна ¹ , САМОБЫТНОСТЬ ЛАНДШАФТНОГО ЗОДЧЕСТВА ДРЕВНИХ ГОРОДИЩ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ И ИХ ГРАДОФОРМИРУЮЩЕЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ	28-33
7.	М.Б. Худоярова, Р.У. Чекаева, ШАҲАРСОЗЛИК ТАМОЙИЛЛАРИ ВА БИНО ИНТЕРЬЕРИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ	34-37
8.	Рабиев Ғайрат Ботирович. ҚИШЛОҚ ЖОЙЛАРИДА ЁШ ОИЛАЛАРГА ЯККА ТАРТИБДА ТУРАРЖОЙ ҚУРИШ УЧУН ЕР МАЙДОНИ АЖРАТИЛИШИГА ДОИР ТАКЛИФ-МУЛОҲАЗАЛАР.	38-41
9.	Гильманова Нафиса Валиахметовна, КВАРТАЛЬНАЯ МЕЧЕТЬ	42-45
10.	Ro‘ziyev Hoshim Ro‘ziyevich , Odilov Akmal Baxshilloyevich, BUXORO SHAHAR HUDUDINI SHAKLLANTIRISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ARXITEKTURA-REJALASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	46-50
11.	Yaxuyayev A.A., Sabirov Orifjon Ikromovich, XORAZM VILOYATI ZAMONAVIY TURAR-JOY MUHITINI SHAKLLANTIRISH VA LANDSHAFT ARXITEKTURASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	51-53
12.	Qurbonov Ravshan Xushnazarovich, ISPANIYA YANGI ARXITEKTURA SHAKLLANISHI: ANTONIO GAUDI	54-58
13.	G'. Shukurov , A.G. Shukurov, M.A. Shukurova, D.G. Islamova , SAMARQAND SHAHRIDA SHAHARSOZLIK BO‘YICHA BUNYODKORLIK ISHLARI.	59-62
14.	Jurayeva Elvira Elmuradovna , Ma‘murjonov Shukrullo Umidjon , RESEARCH OF HISTORICAL CITY CENTERS	63-67
15.	Вахитов М.М., Набиев Хамид , БУХОРО АМИРИНИНГ КОГОН ШАҲРИДАГИ САРОЙИ	68-71
16.	Shakarboy Eliboyevich O‘rinboyev, Dilshoda Mustafayevna Nazarova, O‘ZBEKISTON SHAHARLARIDA ZAMONAVIY BINOLAR KO‘PAYGANLIGI SABABLI SHAHAR LANDSHAFTI VA ISTIROHAT BOG‘LAR SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH OMILLARI	72-75